

LEXICAL-SEMANTIC AND STYLISTIC FEATURES OF ADJECTIVAL DIALECTISM'S IN THE LANGUAGE OF AZERBAIJANI POETRY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17928098>

Summary. *The linguistic analysis of adjectival dialectisms in the language of Azerbaijani poetry demonstrates that they possess wide lexical-semantic and stylistic potential. In poetic texts, such word units not only intensify descriptiveness but also contribute to the formation of artistic imagery and stylistic diversity. The poetic language, along with nominative units within the noun group, is also rich in adjectives that convey the shades of attributes and content of objects and events. A significant part of these adjectives consists of dialect words, the usage of which in poetic texts increases the synonymic potential of the language. The subtle semantic differences between the various qualities of objects and phenomena necessitate the use of adjectival dialectisms in poetic language. Research shows that poets have employed such linguistic units for artistic and aesthetic purposes, thereby expanding the stylistic potential of poetic language. The article provides a comprehensive analysis of the linguistic features of adjectival dialectism's.*

Keywords: *dialectism, linguistics, poetic language, lexicon, semantics.*

Introduction

In the expressive system of poetry, i.e., in its structural-semantic organization, adjectival dialectisms hold a special place. They function both independently and within synonymic rows, playing an invaluable role in the organization of poetic texts and the creation of various stylistic shades. The expansion of the stylistic-grammatical potential of poetic language is also significantly influenced by adjectival dialectisms. Nevertheless, Azerbaijani linguistics has not sufficiently addressed this field on the basis of available poetic materials. This factor defines the relevance of the issue raised in this article.

The use of adjectival dialectisms in poetic texts is intensive in nature. The semantic basis of such linguistic units is formed by categories of attribute and quality. Dialectal variants of adjectives denoting color, space, size, external appearance and physical characteristics of humans and animals, character, behavior and inner psychological traits, and in general both concrete and abstract qualities, perform important stylistic functions in poetic texts.

For instance, in Azerbaijani literary language, the dialectal words "nimdaş" and "boyat", belonging to the synonymic row of the adjective "köhnə" (old), are employed in poetry for stylistic purposes:

You remove from your body

Hopes, beliefs,

Hallmarks, sins,

They fall like a nimdaş (worn-out) garment [2, 77].

In the poetic examples selected from the works of Vagif Samedoghlu, the adjectival dialectisms "nimdaş" and "boyat" serve as linguistic units that more precisely describe the quality of objects. Although these lexical units are semantically close, they differ in stylistic nuance. For example, "nimdaş" cannot be applied to bread, while "boyat" (stale) creates

semantic incompatibility if used for clothing. This clearly demonstrates their stylistic-semantic differentiation.

According to the syntactic norm in the Azerbaijani language, an adjective always precedes a noun. However, in poetic language this rule may be intentionally broken for poetic-aesthetic purposes. For instance, in the phrase "çörək boyat" (bread stale), the adjective follows the noun, which, although outside the norm, does not create a logical contradiction. On the contrary, it turns into a natural form that enriches the poet's artistic expression and the expressive possibilities of the language.

In this respect, it is appropriate to recall A. Shcherbak's idea: "...the determination of the adjective is the result of the semantic-functional transformation of nouns" [1, 18].

The adjective "nimdaş" is used in the dialects of Chambarak, Yerevan, Kalinino, and Karakilsa in Western Azerbaijan in the meaning of "worn, used clothing or fabric" [3, 289]. These facts show that this dialectism, formed within certain spatial and domestic contexts, stands out in poetic texts with its lexical-semantic specificity.

Conclusion: The observations carried out prove that adjectival dialectisms are widely manifested in the morphological system of poetic language. These linguistic units not only serve a descriptive function but also act as important stylistic elements that determine the lyrical content and aesthetic value of poetic texts. Adjectival dialectisms bring the poetic description closer to natural spoken communication, enhance imagery and emotional impact, and strengthen the artistic-aesthetic effect of poetry. Thus, adjectival dialectisms can be evaluated as a crucial factor ensuring the structural-semantic richness of poetic language, both linguistically and poetically.

LİTERATURE

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